

SOCIAL MEDIA AND CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT WITH SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ABASIFREKE IDIONG, PhD

Department of Journalism, University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria
+234 8175380510, Email: abasifrekeidiong@uniuyo.edu.ng

GODWIN MATTHEW INYIENG, PhD

Department of Journalism, University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria
+234 8033820231, Email: godwininyiengchairmanuk2020@gmail.com

NJAH BASSEY ETTA

Department of Mass Communication
University of Cross River State, Calabar, Nigeria
+234 8094439622, Email: njahbasseyyetta@crutech.edu.ng

&

BLESSING GODWIN EDET

Department of Mass Communication, Benin, Edo State, Nigeria
+234 9095315938, Email: blessingedet1963@gmail.com

Abstract

Citizen engagement in scientific and technological issues is in vogue in recent years, and a variety of approaches intended to popularize science, technology and innovation (STI) and engender greater public understanding, participation and utilization of STI are occurring worldwide. Scholars and policy makers have increasingly advocated engaging citizens more substantially in the development of science and technology, and many Nigerian science and technology organizations are tending to promote science-citizen dialogue via the use of social media. This research, therefore, is a qualitative evaluation of the social media handles, accounts and pages of selected STI organizations in Nigeria to ascertain the deployment or otherwise of social media for the purpose of engaging with the public. Science communication in Nigeria is still fragile and agency-public engagement for most science organizations is frail, except for some efforts on Facebook. Thus, this paper calls on Nigerian STI institutions to appraise the pragmatics of their public engagement in order to help popularize STI and engenders the public to understand and utilize it.

Keywords: Social media, Citizen Engagement, Science, Technology, Innovation, Webpages, Interactive features, Hyperlinks

Introduction

Digital networking platforms or social media have gained traction among Nigerians as a tool not only for enacting and consolidating social interactions and transactions for filial, emotional, psychological and workplace relationships, but also a potent platform for obtaining, generating and disseminating information; an avenue to learn and educate, and a forum to apprehend and interrogate new ideas, including knowledge about science and technology.

Zack (2017) notes that social media enables scholars to escape the confines of libraries and journals by disseminating research results to a wider audience, and doing so faster. The instantaneous access to research results makes them more accessible to the public and increases the impacts to an interdisciplinary and broader audience. Pustinen and Edwards (2012) found that by tweeting first about their new research, the science paper was downloaded 861 times in 24 hours; long before any other promotion was available.

There is no gainsaying the fact that social media has changed the global science and technology communication landscapes around the world. Social media users reached 2.46 billion people globally in 2017. To put that in perspective, 2.46 billion is approximately six times the population of the United States (324 million in 2017) and about a third of the global population (7.3 billion). A social report cited in Sekhon and Krause (2018) places it at 80,000 Internet users worldwide, suggesting that over 41% of people use social media to stay informed on current news or events.

Nigeria does boast of multiplicity of science, technology and innovation institutions saddled with the responsibilities of conducting researches, producing science, technology and innovation (STI) knowledge and promoting the same for both experts and non-experts consumption. This is to help popularize STI and engender public understanding and utilization of STI.

However, with the acute paucity of research data on science communication as a result of science communication fragility in Nigeria, we cannot tell, without empirical research, the extent to which the burgeoning social media outlook in Nigeria has been harnessed by Nigerian STI organizations for the purpose of engagement with the Nigerian public. Without doubts, citizen engagement with STI is an important ingredient in promoting health/disease prevention, reduction of poverty, entrenchment of a literate society, economic regeneration, environmental protection and human development, generally.

Science communication cultures differ around the world. While science communication in the developed societies has made considerable inroads in advancing the cause of making science production and promotion people-centered, sadly, science communication culture in Africa remains fragile. As Dutta and Batta (2013, p. 31) note, “seen from the parameters of national science communication infrastructure, political attention, actors involved, the academic tradition, attitude to science knowledge acquisition, and the science journalism situation, Africa, particularly sub-Saharan Africa, except perhaps, South Africa, is not doing well.” According to Marina Joubert (2009), who cited Prof Mohammed Hassan of the Academy of Science for the Developing World in Dutta and Batta, Africa trails behind with regards to the generation of new knowledge.

Social media holds great promise for science and technology communication. However, in spite of the professional and growing benefits of social media, many scientists are reluctant to use them for work. Developing a useful digital and engaging footprint is time-consuming and many unconvinced scientists and agencies struggle to fit this into their already heavy schedules. Moreover, the ubiquity of social media and its ability to break geographical barriers means that its use may blur the line between work and personal life. Some science and technology institutions have also voiced concerns and are increasingly wary and cautious of stepping into the world of social media. Their concerns bother on confidentiality, privacy, misrepresentation and bad publicity that could go viral in minutes.

Though science communication is fairly novel in Nigeria, a cursory assessment of the Nigerian media landscape - print: newspaper and magazine, broadcast: radio and television, and the digital media - indicates that Nigerians engage in science and technology communication. Dutta and Batta, however, observe that science journalism (even in Nigeria) is gravitating towards the Internet. According to them,

Living in the digital age has come to mean that people are increasingly turning to the internet for news, other bits of information and cultural needs. For a substantial number of people, the priority medium of information acquisition has shifted from newspapers, magazines, books, radio and television to the Internet. Science centers, museums, science institutes, science clearing houses, research centers, and universities have taken advantage of this.

Against this backdrop, it is thought that social media imbue scientists with a broader diversity of coverage, reach and perspectives, as well as afford citizens greater opportunity to understand and utilize STI. The outcome of this research would provide the template for gauging the contributions of the social media to the advancement of public learning and understanding of science and technology. This research gap and its implication for development provide the rationale for this paper.

Statement of the Problem

Science communication has evolved into a potent aspect of the public outreach and education programmes of many scientific organizations. Where television documentaries and public exhibitions were once relied upon for these aims, social media platforms have now brought new opportunities for scientists and communicators to interact with their audiences. It is estimated that on a given day, 50% of Facebook's 500-million plus users log-on to social networking sites. The average user is connected to 80 community pages, groups, and events, and creates about 90 pieces of content for posting each month. Twitter's 200 million users are also thought to produce around 110 million tweets per day on topics ranging from celebrity gossips, breaking news about disasters, developments, technology and innovations. Factoring in equally engaging platforms like LinkedIn, Instagram, and YouTube equates the masses. What is important to note is that millions of people all over the world are constantly sharing an extremely wide range of fascinating, quirky, funny, irrelevant and important contents all at once. Scientists are not left out in this frenzy. Social media enables them to communicate their research quickly, efficiently, in real time and on a global scale. Nigerian STI institutions such as National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), National Space Research and Development Agency (NASRDA), National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA) and National Office for Technology Acquisition and Promotion (NOTAP) are known to employ some social media tools for communicating, propagating, popularizing and engaging citizens in their bid to engender understanding and utilization of STI.

Given that social media plays such an integral part in our life, the question arises: which social media platforms are STI organizations using to communicate their research, how are they using them and to what extent are Nigerian citizens engaging with science and technology using social media?

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were to:

- (i) ascertain the depth of social media penetration in Nigeria;

- (ii) ascertain the extent to which Nigerian science and technology organizations deploy social media for public promotion of STI;
- (iii) find out the extent to which Nigerian science and technology organizations and the Nigerian public engage each other on the social media

Literature Review

Concept of social media

The first decade of the new millennium witnessed a new quality of the social impact of digitization. With the establishment of social media like Facebook (2004) and Twitter (2006), the conditions of the sundry aspects of human communication have been fundamentally transformed. What is called social media is subsumed under web 2.0. The concept is used to describe the second stage of the Internet, characterized by the change from static web pages to dynamic or user-generated content and the growth of social networks. Web 2.0 refers to web pages that emphasize ease of use, interaction, greater citizen engagement, participatory culture and interoperability for end users.

The collective term “social media” for such formats has been established in practice as well as scientific courses. Social media include individual formats like blogs and podcasts (usually operated by a person or an organization), as well as collective formats like social network sites (SNS) for example, Facebook. Microblogging services (example, Twitter), video and photography platforms (for example, YouTube, Instagram) and wikis (for example, Wikipedia), where a great number of networked users collaborate within a single service.

Social media, Scientists and Public Engagement

Social media now complements many parts of our lives. Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and many other social networking sites allow users to share and interact with online content and to connect with like-minded people. Its strengths - rapid dissemination and amplification of content and the ability to lead informal conversations - make it a powerful tool to use in a professional context. In spite of the above, social media carries the stigma of frivolous time wasting activity and many scientists are reluctant to engage with it in a professional context. Common reasons for scientists not to engage with social media include the fear of appearing unprofessional, posting something wrong or being misunderstood, or a lack of confidence in their computer skills. Other barriers include concerns around copyright and legal issues, different research discipline cultures or personal barriers (Osterrieder 2013).

Conversely, social media is a powerful professional tool for scientists when used appropriately and efficiently. For instance, with the rapid changes in academic publishing, dissemination of information and science communication, as well as what Osterrieder (2013) described as the rise of ‘altmetrics’ to track online engagement with science content, many STI policy makers are having a rethinking. Social media has been found to help close the gap between scientific discovery and its translation to medical application (Sandalova, Ledford and Baskaran, 2019), which the authors admit have had immense contributions on institutional policy on the professional use of social media.

In its simplest case, social media can provide a highly personalized and relevant “table of content” to keep up to date with current research, popular science and broader issues such as science policy, funding, publishing, or personal career development. Certain social media platforms can offer invaluable tools for networking, either within specific subject fields or across different disciplines and professions. These open platforms enable dialogue not only between scientists, but also for others (science communicators and journalists, teachers, students, researchers, and professionals from other disciplines, as well as other interested non-experts) to join the conversation. Osterrieder sums up the argument by noting that actively participating in social media networks allows scientists to disseminate research findings quickly and effectively as well as raise their own profile and those of their research groups or institutions. More importantly, the interactive nature of the medium can be highly beneficial for scientists by offering new perspectives on their research and ensuring the greatest public good. However, while a percentage retain a healthy skepticism about social media use and some scientists are increasingly embracing social media in their professional lives, one thing is clear: the range of social media platforms that scientists and science agencies are using is relatively vast and dependent on discipline and sentiments, particularly when it comes to mainstream social networking sites like Twitter, Facebook and YouTube.

An Overview of some Science and Technology Agencies in Nigeria National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA)

The National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) was created in April 2001 to implement the Nigerian Information Technology Policy and coordinate general IT development in the country. The National Information Technology Development Act (2007) mandates the agency to create a framework for the planning, research, development, standardization, application, coordination, monitoring, evaluation and regulation of Information Technology practices,

activities and systems in Nigeria. The agency is also saddled with the responsibility of developing, regulating and advising on Information Technology in the country through regulatory standards, guidelines and policies. Additionally, NITDA is the clearing house for all IT projects and infrastructural development in the country. It is the prime Agency for e-government implementation, Internet governance and general IT development in Nigeria. NITDA says it actualizes its mammoth mandate through strategic and inclusive stakeholder management, local and international partnership and efficient utilization of resources in the interest of Nigeria. The agency lists as its vision the task of proactively facilitating the development of Nigeria into a sustainable digital economy. It says this responsibility makes it Nigeria's apex IT Agency that creates an enabling environment where Nigerians develop, adopt and derive value from digital technology.

National Space Research and Development Agency (NASRDA)

The National Space Research and Development Agency (NASRDA) is the national space agency of Nigeria. It is a parastatal under the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology. The agency is based in the Nigerian capital city of Abuja in the Lugbe district and has a ground receiving station, among various other sites. It has had cooperation in space technology with the United Kingdom, China, Ukraine and Russia. The agency has struggled with meeting its financial plans and some of its facilities are rundown. Despite this, the space agency is one of the most advanced space agencies in Africa, boasting of four satellites and very grand ambitions. Nigeria's satellites have been praised for their high-resolution images. NASRDA is host to one of UN-SPIDER's Regional Support Offices (RSO) in Africa.

NASRDA was established on 5th May 1999, after a preparation period since 1998 by Nigerian president Olusegun Obasanjo and the Nigerian government with a primary objective of establishing a "fundamental policy for the development of space science and technology" with an initial budget of \$93 million. In May 2006, the new extended national space program was adopted. NASRDA has launched four satellites of its own, the first one in 2003 and the last one in 2009. The organisation faced a media meltdown in 2016 once it was announced that Nigeria would send an astronaut to space by 2030. This caused many reactions across the Internet, even from many experts on the African space industry. Many Nigerians believed that this was a waste of money.

The initial scope of the Nigerian Space Programme (NSP) to be implemented by the National Space Research and Development Agency (NASRDA) was thought to

include the study of basic space science in order to lay the foundation for deriving maximum benefits from the nation's participation in the space enterprise; focus on research and rigorous education, engineering development, design and manufacture, particularly in the areas of instrumentation, rocketry and small satellites as well as in satellite data acquisition, processing, analysis and management of related software in order to attain space capabilities; and the establishment of a national earth observation station for remote sensing and satellite meteorology data acquisition.

The focus areas of the Nigerian Space Programme (NSP) include:

Basic Space Science and Technology: to provide the understanding of how the universe works and what its impact is on the world. This will enable us to lay the foundation for deriving maximum benefits from the nation's participation in the space enterprise.

Remote Sensing: to help Nigerians understand and manage the environment and natural resources using space-acquired information. This technology will enable us to better understand our land, air and water resources and their associated problems.

Satellite Meteorology: to study atmospheric and weather sciences using satellite data to facilitate the effective management of our environment.

Communication and Information Technology: to provide efficient and reliable telecommunications services for Nigeria in order to enhance the growth of the industrial, commercial and administrative sectors of the economy.

Defense and Security: to help the Federal Government develop a necessary Space Science Technology (SST) programme that will address the national needs of Nigeria. For this purpose, the government established a Defense Space Command in the Ministry of Defense.

National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA)

In recognition of the importance of biotechnology to national development, the Federal Executive Council, on 23rd of April 2001, approved the National Biotechnology Policy which led to the establishment of the National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA) in November 2001. The Agency was established under the aegis of the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology to implement the policy that is aimed at promoting, coordinating, and setting research and development priority in biotechnology for Nigeria. Based on this premise, the

programmes of the agency are structured in line with the international standard, bearing in mind the development of local technological contents.

The agency has the mandate for the research and development, promotion, coordination and deployment of cutting-edge biotechnology processes, and products for the socio-economic well-being of the nation. Listing its vision to include making Biotechnology an engine of growth for socio-economic development of Nigeria, the agency prides itself as being on the mission of promoting biotechnology activities that positively respond to national aspirations on food security, job/wealth creation, affordable healthcare delivery and sustainable environment.

National Office for Technology Acquisition and Promotion (NOTAP)

The National Office for Technology Acquisition and Promotion (NOTAP) was established by Decree No. 70 of 1979 as an agency under the aegis of the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology as the National Office of Industrial Property (NOIP). It is a corporate body with a mandate to implement the acquisition, promotion and development of technology and at the same time correct certain imperfections in the acquisition of foreign technology into the country. In 1992, the name of the Office was changed to National Office for Technology Acquisition and Promotion (NOTAP) by Decree No. 82 of 1992. This was to ensure that the name adequately reflects the entire functions of the Office and to also remove any ambiguity or misconception that may rise in relation to any other Government agency.

In line with globalization and liberalization of the world economy, NOTAP has shifted its emphasis from regulatory and control to promotional and developmental roles. The new areas of focus are aimed at attracting foreign technologies and investment and the development of indigenous technology. NOTAP was, therefore, established as one of the main instruments to carry out the National Policy on Technology Development. Part of this policy stipulates the encouragement of the flow of technology into the country in order to strengthen industrial development and encourage domestic enterprises to acquire foreign technologies that are suitable to the local environment.

NOTAP lists its mandate to include encouragement of a more efficient process for the identification and selection of foreign technology; development of the negotiating skills of Nigerians with a view to ensuring the acquisition of the best contractual terms and conditions in the transfer of foreign technology agreements; provision of a

more efficient process for the adaptation of imported technology; promotion and encouragement of the development of creative and inventive skills among Nigerian scientists, researchers, inventors and innovators, among others.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is anchored on the theory of Citizen Participation. Effective citizen engagement is generally accepted as one of the most important steps towards making science and technology meaningful to the public. Citizen participation is a process which provides private individuals an opportunity to influence public decisions. The roots of this theory can be traced to ancient Greece and colonial New England. Cogan and Sharpe (1986, p. 283) say citizen participation was institutionalized in the mid-1960s and that government processes and procedures were designed to facilitate external participation.

Proponents of the theory had argued that it was counterproductive for agencies, both public and private, to minimize public participation in planning efforts, claiming citizen participation was too expensive and time consuming. Making a case for greater citizen participation programmes, they contend that there are tangible benefits that can be derived from an effective citizen participation programme. Cogan and Sharpe (1986, p. 284) have identified benefits of citizen engagement to include information and ideas on public issues, public support for planning decisions, avoidance of protracted conflicts and costly delays, reservoir of goodwill which can carry over to future decisions, and spirit of cooperation and trust between an agency and the public.

Since then, several adaptations, ferments and extensions have evolved. One school of thought says citizen participation should not be an end in itself, but a unique ingredient in the overall goal. This position has tended to be popularized by proponents who see far-reaching prospects in science-public engagement. Bringing development via science, innovation and technology to the public is one of the main pillars of the welfare State, and one good that has the capacity to better human living. Without citizen engagement, these prospects are unrealizable, for as the authors note, citizens are increasingly expected to take a more participatory role in society which increases the need for them to be knowledgeable about a wide range of uncertain risks and to properly prepare themselves in case those risks become reality.

Methodology

To address the research objectives, the study relied on literature searches to determine the status of social media depth in Nigeria. The researchers then conducted a qualitative content analysis of the social media handles, accounts and pages of selected STI organizations in Nigeria. The content analysis helped ascertain the deployment or otherwise of the social media by Nigerian STI organizations. The units of analysis included science and technology social media pages, accounts and handles containing interactive features, hyperlinks, audience traffic features, as well as video and sound click analytics. While the researchers acknowledge the existence of a trove of social media platforms, this study is based on the agencies' presence on Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and Instagram. Where a science agency has its WhatsApp contact linked to their webpages, this is given a mention.

Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Whether to follow friends, family, acquaintances, or actors and people in the arts and entertainment industry, or stay in touch with developments in science and technology, social media usage in Nigeria has been on the rise in recent years. For most users, the aim is to keep in touch with close relations. Therefore, it is not surprising that WhatsApp is the most used social media platform in the country. As of the third quarter of 2021, this instant messaging and voice-over-IP platform was used by nearly 92 percent of Nigeria's overall Internet users, ahead of Facebook and Instagram. However, Facebook was the most preferred platform for the majority of individuals accessing the news on social media (Sasa 2002).

As of January 2022, Nigeria with a projected population of well over 200 million had 32.9 million active social media users. WhatsApp retained its place as the most popular platform used in the country, with over 90 million users. Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram followed as the most used social media platforms in Nigeria (Sasa 2022).

Social media diffusion and use is consequent upon Internet user penetration in any given society. Sasa has mapped a trajectory of Internet use in Nigeria from 2018(28.75%), 2019 (33.42%), 2020 (34.55%), 2021 (36.67%), of which about 33 million are active users. According to the author, men constitute the most active population group (58.3%), with 18-34 year olds the most reached by social media advertising. Sasa (2022) further ranks social media users in Nigeria by platform thus: Facebook, 34,608,200; Instagram, 9,978,000; Messenger, 27,572,600; Linkedin, 6,475,000. From all indications, social media penetration in Nigeria has not shown any signs of decline over the last decade.

NITDA has a burgeoning Internet presence that gives life to her social media engagements when compared to the other science agencies studied. A simple click on the agency's website ushers users into the full complement of their web 2.0 presence, namely Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, LinkedIn, WhatsApp and even email address. It is safe to submit that the agency uses the platforms fairly optimally. On Facebook alone, NITDA boast a commanding 167, 000 following (on an account that permits instant real time call and messaging). Visitors to the site are treated to several interactive pop ups and hyperlinks containing videos and soundbites and 'contact us' blinks with dialogue boxes that redirect users to the individual social media platforms of the agency. NITDA's webpages also hosts an analytic of audience traffic.

It takes an average of 10 minutes to get a response to any user generated content queries on any of NITDA's handles, accounts or pages. On Facebook, NITDA hosts a weekly participatory programme that highlights the activities of the agency in line with the national digital economic policy and strategy; and this User Generated Contents (UGC) suggests this has been a remarkable success in popularising science and technology and engaging netizens with useful information. For instance, NITDA's (December 22, 2022) edition of the programme hosted live attracted over 4,000 views and several real time responses to enquiries from Facebook users. The agency has 148,000 followers on Twitter and has been consistent in keeping traffic on the handle with news and tidbits on science, technology and innovation. One of the strengths of NITDA on Twitter is it's ability to offer on the spot answers to enquiries and queries. NITDA is not faring as well on YouTube where it has 1.48k subscribers, 124 videos and 77,958 cumulative viewing hours since joining the platform on September 5, 2013. What is lacking in NITDA's YouTube experience is real dialogue with viewers, as is the case with its Facebook account. Videos are just streamed with little recourse to the concerns of viewers. This calls for immediate action. NITDA's Instagram public engagement is relatively robust. With 14,000 followers, over 1600 posts and real time interface with followers, it is safe to conclude that NITDA as a Nigerian science and technology organization deploys social media considerably for promotion of public science, technology and innovation and uses same to engage with and make science and technology useful to the Nigerian public and could do better.

NOTAP social media engagements leaves so much to be desired. 170 reactions in all of 2022 from a paltry 30 Facebook posts using an unverified account is definitely not a good return on investment. That is an average of five reactions per post and the agency could manage just 17 comments all year. That is appalling and very disappointing. NOTAP has 56 followers on Instagram, with its last post made in September 2022 attracting one like. The agency joined Twitter in April 2016 and has zero engagement with citizens. Notap has no known YouTube channel.

NASRDA has an unverified Facebook page created since 2015. And despite being in existence for about eight years, the agency has made only three Facebook posts. The agency has no engagements with the public. In fact, it is worrisome to note that in spite of repeated petitions in their comment section by one Murtala Abdullahi bordering on fraud by her staff, the agency has not made any response. Like her Facebook account, NASRDA's Instagram account is not verified. The agency has made 90 posts to date, with little or no attempts at engaging followers or responding to queries and enquiries. NASRDA has some semblance of presence on YouTube which it joined in 2018 but audience engagement is poor.

NABDA floats both the conventional Facebook account and a page. NABDA responsive engagement with followers on Facebook is topnotch. Aside reacting to all comments, the agency also responds to inquiries in timely and courteous fashion. NABDA's Facebook traffic between January 2022 and 2023 has been in thousands. NABDA's engagement on Instagram is equally robust, but with a paltry 62 subscribers on YouTube, 17 videos with 400 views and no reaction or response to user generated contents. NABDA's periodic interactive video reports on research breakthrough for national development is a major attraction to social media handles, but the agency has work to do in staying up to date with audience comments and enquiries, if it is to help Nigerians make sense of STI.

Conclusion/Recommendations

The last decade has completely re-shaped the way in which we communicate. It has become clear that Internet-based communication is growing and all fields of life have to adapt to its use, including the science and technology community. Social media engagement forms a large part of Internet-based communication and plays a crucial role in science, technology and innovation (STI) information sharing, discussion and implementation of discoveries and will continue to evolve. Even though specific platforms will change in the future, the concept of social media is likely to stay. This holds great promise for science institutes and the public. For the scientist, it will become more and more important to engage with social media and become 'digitally literate' rather than avoiding or resisting its use at all, as the rapid changes in science information dissemination and the need to track and engage the burgeoning online demography with science content and digital literacy will become an essential skill in a scientist's tool kit (Osterreider 2013). This would also mean going beyond Facebook and taking advantage of other social media platforms. This paper calls on Nigerian science community to adapt and utilize the vast benefits and novel opportunities that social media offers in order to bring development to where the people are.

References

- Cogan, C. and Sharpe, G. (1986). Planning Analysis: The Theory of Citizen Participation. <https://pages.uoregon.edu/rgp/PPPM613/class10theory.htm>. Accessed September, 2022.
- Dutta, A. and Batta, H. (2013). Theoretical and practical aspects of science communication around the world. In: D. Wilson and H. Batta (Eds.) *Science, Health & Environmental Communication: Global Issues & Local Perspectives*. Ibadan: Ibadan University Press
- Osterrieder, A. (2013). The value and use of social media as communication tool in the plant sciences. *Plant Methods*, 9, 26. <http://plantmethods.com/content/9/1/26>. Accessed August, 19, 2022.
- Pustinen, K and R. Edwards. (2012). Who gives a tweet? After 24 hours and 860 downloads, we think quite a few actually do. <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2012/05/18/who-gives-a-tweet-860-downloads/>. Accessed July, 2022.
- Sandalova, E. Ledford, J. G. and Baskaran, M. (2019). Translational Medicine in the Era of Social Media: A Survey of Scientific and Clinical Communities. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 7, 20. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmed.2019.00152/full>. Accessed August, 10, 2022.
- Sasa, G. (2002). Number of social media users in Nigeria. <https://www.sasa.com/statistics/1176096/number-of-social-media-users-nigeria/2002>. Accessed September, 2022.
- Sekhon, N. Krause, S. (2018). Social Media: changing the science communication landscape. *Texas Geosciences*. Available at: <https://www.jsg.utexas.edu/science-yall/social-media-landscape/>. Accessed July 2022.
- Zack, L. (2017). Social Media and digital science Communication. https://www.acatech.de/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/WOM2_EN_web_final.pdf. Accessed July, 2022.